

Opinions of teachers working in private schools on creating and developing organizational culture

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Abstract. With this research, it was aimed to understand and interpret the opinions of the teachers working in private schools on creating school culture and ensuring its continuity. According to the opinions of the participants in the study, the concept of culture in schools, teachers' commitment to the organization, the motivation of belonging, the effect of organizational culture on teacher motivation and what should be done to improve the organizational culture were studied. In the research case study design used. The study group of the research consists of 15 teachers working in Private Antalya Final schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in the Kepez district of Antalya province. In the research, the data were collected using a semi-structured interview form consisting of 5 (five) open-ended questions developed by the researcher in order to get the opinions and evaluations of the teachers about the concept of organizational culture and the effects of this concept on the teacher and the organization. In the analysis of qualitative data, the data obtained from the interviews with the teachers were coded. According to the results obtained from the research, it was understood that organizational culture had a very important place in the formation and development of the structure of organizations and the power of organizational culture was very effective in determining the permanence and continuity of organizations and the quality of the service produced.

Keywords: Special education, schools, principals, teachers

Introduction

School culture differs in terms of formation and continuity depending on many components. First of all, when we have a look at what comes to mind in academic literature when school culture is mentioned; school culture consists of school rules, beliefs and values that guide the behavior of administrators, teachers and students in a school (Richard, 1999). School culture is the organization that consists of values, belief patterns and traditions formed in the process since the establishment of the school. According to Deal and Peterson (1998, 1999) school culture is the actions and values that direct the common sharing of all stakeholders (administrators, teachers and students) and their activities within the school. According to Heckman (1993), school culture is the whole of elements that reflect the in-depth application and character of the traditions, beliefs and values established since the founding of the school. The factors that determine school culture can be listed as follows: age of the school, historical development process of the school, purpose and objectives of the school, socio-economic and geographical environment in which the school is located, socio-economic levels of the students, rural and urban areas, school facilities, the technology used in the school, the size of the school and class, the expectations of the administrators, teachers and students, the expectations of the parents, the centrality of the education system, whether the educational organizations are private or not, the structure of the education system (Gaziel, 1997).

In order for the school culture to have a strong and effective identity, it must have the following features:

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- **Shared Values:** These values are open to everyone in the organization and permeate every activity that the organization produces and performs. Values are often not written down, but they emerge in the school's practices. Because values, curricula, teaching methods, time planning and management, reward-punishment system guide the stakeholders of the organization in many issues.
- **Humor:** The climate of life in the school, personal intimacy, the amount of joy and happiness depend on a strong culture. Humor and joy are indicators of people in the organization gaining experience in the face of difficulties.
- **Storytelling:** There are stories embedded in every organization, including schools. The stories that are told and need to be told are about culture. These stories told in the form of legends reflect the historical perspective of the organization. These stories are both educational, motivating and instructive. In addition, stories and legends can play a binding role among members of the organization.
- **Communication Network:** Every organization and culture has a communication system in order to deliver and disseminate the services produced by the organization and all the achievements to the greatest possible number of people. Here, every manager must know and apply all the means necessary to disseminate information quickly within the system.
- **Rituals and Ceremonies (Ceremonies, Ceremonies):** Rituals in school culture are the whole that affects and expresses the organizational identity such as important days and events, activities, celebrations and commemorations. These run into the cells of the organizational structure. Organizational culture is also tried to be transferred to the members of the organization through ceremonies defined as traditional activities. For example, farewell dinners, meetups, competitions.
- **Relationships Between Colleagues:** positive dialogue between teachers will reflect positively from teacher to student and school environment, and will contribute to the improvement of professional sharing, human values, communication environment and increase the success of the service provided (Pawlas, 1997),

Schools that contain all or almost all of these elements as a culture, whether they are public or private education organizations, have a strong school culture.

The behavior of leaders in organizations, managing and adopting cultural diversity and harmony and balance are leadership skills. The leader must have foresight. What leaders should do for effective cultural management can be listed as follows: strategic planning and determining the cultural infrastructure required by it, making the culture compatible and consistent with the mission, goals, strategies, structure and processes, transforming the philosophy and values of the organization into a written document, consistent incentives, appreciation systems and performance management, creating error detection systems and sanctions, managing coaching, mentoring, training practices, keeping rituals, symbols, company legends alive, utilizing the characteristics of subcultures and supporting and managing successful practices (March and Herbert, 1975).

This research was carried out with the thought that it would contribute to the literature on organizational culture by understanding and interpreting teachers' perspectives on organizational culture and the perception of how the organizational culture would develop in the system they were in, by creating awareness about school culture and the development process of school culture.

Due to the limited number of studies in this field, it is thought that this study will contribute to the practices of a private school by putting the concept of organizational culture with the opinions of teachers at primary, secondary and high school levels. In this respect, the research was based on the question of "What are the teachers' views on the creation and development of organizational culture among teachers working in private schools?" and aimed to reveal "what teachers think about the concept of organizational culture and how organizational culture can be developed in a school". The study sought answers to the following sub-problems according to the teachers' opinions,

1. How do teachers in private schools define organizational culture?

2. How do teachers in private schools define their belonging to the organization?
3. What is the effect of organizational culture on teachers' motivation in private schools?
4. What should be done to improve the existing organizational culture in private schools?
5. What do teachers think the organizational culture of private schools like? Why?

Method and paradigm of research

In this research, the interpretive paradigm was applied. The aim of interpretive research is to understand social phenomena through subjective reasons and meanings (Gunbayi & Sorm, 2018). Qualitative research method and descriptive holistic single case study design (Yin, 2017) were used in this research, which tried to understand and interpret the construction and development of organizational culture among teachers working in private schools. Qualitative research can be defined as research in which techniques such as observation, interview and document analysis are used, and a qualitative process is followed by revealing perceptions and events in a natural environment (Creswell, 2007).

Sampling

The study data consisted of 15 teachers working in a private school located in Kepez district within the borders of Antalya province in the 2022-2023 academic year. Demographic information about the teachers is given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Distribution of demographic variables of the participants

Participant	Gender	Type of School	Graduation
1	Female	High School	Under-graduate
2	Female	Middle School	Under-graduate
3	Female	Middle School	Under-graduate
4	Female	Primary School	Under-graduate
5	Female	Middle School	Under-graduate
6	Female	Middle School	Under-graduate
7	Male	Middle School	Under-graduate
8	Male	Middle School	Under-graduate
9	Male	High School	Under-graduate
10	Male	High School	Under-graduate
11	Female	Middle School	Under-graduate
12	Male	Primary School	Under-graduate
13	Female	Primary School	Under-graduate
14	Male	Middle School	Under-graduate
15	Male	Primary School	Under-graduate

As seen in Table 1, 8 of the teachers in the sampling were female and 7 were male. All of the teachers were undergraduates. Of the teachers, 4 were at the primary school level, 8 middle school level, and high school level.

Data collection

In order to collect data in the research, a semi-structured interview form consisting of 5 open-ended questions developed by the researcher was used in order to understand and interpret the construction and development of organizational culture in teachers working in private schools. During the interview,

the answers were recorded with the permission of the participants. The interview lasted approximately 25-30 minutes.

Ethical procedures

Scientific research ethics were followed at all stages of the research: (1) Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee Approval was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee in the meeting 06 decision numbered 123 on March 25th, 2022, (2) permission was obtained from the private school administration for the implementation of the research and (3) an environment of trust was provided with the consent form with the participants regarding the confidentiality and reliability of the research.

Validity and reliability of the research

In order to increase the internal and external validity and reliability based on the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability, (Lincoln and Guba, 1985) of the qualitative data, followings were carried out: (1) in order to increase the internal validity (credibility) of the research, an interview form was developed by the review of the relevant literature, (2) in order to increase the external validity (transferability) of the research, participants were informed that participation in the research is voluntary, interviews were transcribed verbatim and their accuracy was confirmed by the teachers, (3) in order to increase the internal reliability (confirmability) Cohen's kappa coefficient was calculated to determine inter-rater reliability of themes as 0.87, a perfect level of agreement between the coding, d) In order to increase the external reliability (dependability) of the research, all data collected were kept to prove on demand (Landis and Koach, 1977; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Cohen, Mannion and Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

Data analysis

Interviews with the participants were audio-recorded with the permission of the participants. Later, the audio recordings were transcribed verbatim in order to analyze the recordings. The data obtained as a result of the interviews with the teachers were coded using NVIVO 10 software. The collected data were converted into themes/categories that best described the problem and content analyzes were carried out (Kelle, 1995; Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007). Thus, based on the answers given by the teachers, the data were arranged in a meaningful way with themes, transferred to tables and analyzed by supporting direct quotations from the participants.

Findings

The study findings are presented according to the answers to the five sub-problems as the definition of organizational culture, the definition of the belonging to the organization, the effect of culture on teachers' motivation, to be done to improve the existing organizational culture in private schools and the metaphors related to the organizational culture of private schools by the participants.

1. Definitions of organizational culture

Participants' opinions on the definition of organizational culture are shown as sub-themes in Table 2.

Tablo 2.

Definitions of organizational culture

Themes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	f
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Values		√	√	√	√	√	√		√		√	7	
Vision	√		√		√				√	√		5	
Rules		√		√			√		√			4	
Belonging					√		√		√			4	
Communication	√										√	√	3
Mission			√						√	√			3
Belief						√	√					√	3
Process								√		√			2

As seen in Table 2, seven of the teachers used the definition of values when defining organizational culture, and some of their opinions on this are given below:

“Culture in a school is a set of rules and customs that have become a habit in all special days, daily operations, student-teacher-parent communication, and spread to all times. All the values that have been adopted form the culture.” (T4)

“The vision, mission, beliefs and values of the organization, the attitude of the administrators, the communication of the teachers in the organization express the organizational culture.” (T7)

“Everything from the value judgments of the organization, the understanding of justice, vision, mission, communication with the group and teachers within the organization, to the dress code in the organization's line that has not changed over the years, expresses the organizational culture.” (I1)

Five of the teachers used the definition of vision while defining organizational culture, and some of their opinions on this are given below:

“The vision of the organization, its mission, the communication of the administration with the teacher, the education system of the organization, everything expresses the organizational culture.” (T3)

“Organizational culture in private schools is a concept that shows the vision of that school, nourishes the sense of belonging for its employees, triggers the desire to produce, increases cooperation between teachers, responds to the wishes of parents and students, and ensures that the adopted values are applied under equal conditions for everyone.” (T5)

“Organizational culture in private schools is defined by teachers as concepts such as education, behavior, and communication adopted by everyone from the administrative manager to security, including students and their parents, in short, everyone who has a mission and vision.”(I2)

Four of the teachers used the definition of rules when defining organizational culture, and some of their opinions on this are given below:

“Culture in a school is the set of rules and customs that have become a habit in all special days, in the daily process of that school, in the rules in student-teacher-parent communication, and spread over all times.”(T4)

“Organizational culture is loyalty to the organization and the rules are taken together and spirituality is at the forefront. ” (S9)

Four of the teachers used the definition of belonging while describing the organizational culture, and some of their opinions are given below:

“Organizational culture does not consist of mandatory rules, of course. It starts with feeling and being made to belong to school.” (7)

“Organizational culture is loyalty to the organization and the rules are taken together and spirituality is at the forefront.” (S9)

Three of the teachers used the definition of communication while describing the organizational culture, and some of their opinions about it are given below:

“As a private school teacher, a large part of the organizational culture is communication. Communication should be effective both with the administrators and within the group.” (T1)

“Communication is one of the indispensable factors in defining organizational culture. Having a high level of communication network in an organization is the most important thing in the formation and maintenance of the organizational culture, where all employees work together for communication.” (14)

Three of the teachers used the definition of mission while defining the organizational culture, and some of their opinions are given below:

“The vision of the organization, its mission, the communication of the administration with the teacher, the education system of the organization, everything expresses the organizational culture.” (T3)

“Organizational culture in private schools is defined by teachers as concepts such as education, behavior and communication adopted by everyone who has a mission and vision, from the administrative manager to security, including students and their parents.” (12)

Three of the teachers used the definition of belief when describing the organizational culture, and some of their opinions on this are given below:

“As a private school teacher, our organizational culture is a set of values and beliefs that are formed and shared with the contributions of administrators, teachers and other employees.” (T6)

“It is the basic rule for all employees of the organization to believe in the organization and to have full faith in the work done for the formation and continuation of the organizational culture.” (15)

Finally, two of the teachers used the definition of process while defining the organizational culture, and one of the opinions is given below:

“Organizational culture is primarily included in our perceptions as the internal process of the relevant organization and the system they implement.” (T8)

2. Definitions of belonging to organizations

Participants’ opinions on the definition of belonging to organizations are shown as sub-themes in Table 3.

Table 3.

Definitions of belonging to organizations

Themes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	f
Confidence			√	√	√									√	√	5
Materiality		√					√			√		√				4
Spirit		√					√					√				3
Communication	√		√								√					3
Value				√	√					√						3

Happiness		√		√	2
Sacrifice		√		√	2
Period	√				2
Appreciate	√				1

As seen in Table 3, five of the teachers defined belonging to the organization as trust, and some of their opinions are given below:

"Belonging to the organization is about the teacher feeling safe." (T3)

"Teacher's working in an environment of trust for the formation of his/her belonging to the organization is formed by valuing his ideas and the rules and initiatives he has determined for his lesson." (T4)

"The sense of belonging to the organization is not a concept that can be formed unilaterally by the teacher, but rather a phenomenon that can be formed in an environment of mutual trust and value, which should be determined according to the quality of the work done rather than personal relationships." (T5)

Four of the teachers stated that material and financial well-being was necessary for the formation of belonging to the organization, and some of some of their opinions are given below:

"Supporting the teacher financially or morally from the school when he has a problem, not ignoring his problems makes the person feel good and strengthens the bond between him and the organization he works for." (T2)

"Teachers in private schools mostly do not feel the organizational culture as their own due to financial reasons and livelihood concerns and they do not perceive this belonging as their priority." (T10)

"While the economic conditions should be taken into consideration in terms of material, the organizational culture should intersect with the culture of the teacher in terms of spirituality." (T12)

Three of the teachers stated that it was necessary to provide spirit and moral support for the formation of belonging to the organization, and some of their opinions are given below:

"The relationship of the teacher with the organization affects the teacher both mentally and physically. When the teacher has a problem, being supported financially or morally by the school, not ignoring the problems cause the person to feel good and strengthen the bond between him and the organization he works for." (T2)

"Belonging to the organization starts with motivation. By getting the reward of your efforts materially and morally and being appreciated." (T7)

Three of the teachers stated that communication was necessary and important for the formation of belonging to the organization, and some of their opinions on this are given below:

"Mutual understanding, communication increases the sense of belonging." (T1)

"In addition, student and parent communication plays an important role in the teacher's ownership of the organization." (T3)

Three of the teachers stated that it was necessary and important to make them feel valuable for the formation of belonging to the organization, and some of their opinions are given below:

“The sense of belonging to the organization is not a concept that can be formed unilaterally by the teacher, but rather a phenomenon that can be formed in an environment of mutual trust and value, which should be determined according to the quality of the work done rather than personal relationships.” (T5)

"Comfortable working environment, giving importance to everyone's opinion, making joint decisions at the end and making them feel valued reveal a sense of belonging in the teacher." (T9)

Two of the teachers stated that belonging to the organization was necessary and important to be happy in the organization, and one of their opinions is given below:

“The sense of belonging to the organization is simply being happy there.” (T8)

Two of the teachers stated that the sense of belonging to the organization came from self-sacrifice, and one of their opinions is given below:

“Although the concept of organizational culture and belonging is formed in many different professions and business areas, it is much more important in teaching because it is a profession that is based on self-sacrifice and can fundamentally affect the future of many children and young people.” (T6)

Two of the teachers stated that belonging to the organization would be in the process, one of their opinions is given below:

“Belonging to the organization is a process that occurs during the time worked in the organization.” (T5)

One of the teachers stated that belonging to the organization would be appreciated by the organization, and the opinion is given below:

“Appreciation also affects the sense of belonging. A teacher who is appreciated becomes attached to his organization and his job.” (T1)

3. The effect of organizational culture on teacher motivation

Participants’ opinions on the effect of organizational culture on teacher motivation are shown as sub-themes in Table 4.

Table 4.

The effect of organizational culture on teacher motivation

Themes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	f
Confidence					√	√	√				√		√			5
Appreciate	√	√								√						3
Happiness					√						√				√	3
Materiality								√				√				2
Seeing Value				√					√							2
Acceptance			√											√		2
Student Success						√										1

As seen in Table 4, five of the teachers stated that confidence in the organization increased teacher motivation. Some of their opinions are given below:

"Teachers' positive communication with their colleagues and administrators in their schools seems to motivate them." (T6)

"Providing organizational culture helps us teachers to gain commitment to the organization, feel safe, work willingly, not out of necessity, promote the organization successfully outside and work in harmony with other employees." (T7)

"Because he will feel safe, he continues to work at the school where the common denominators are intense, he does not need to look for another organization and he produces more." (11)

Three of the teachers stated that being appreciated in the organization increased teacher motivation. Some of their opinions are given below:

"The appreciation that comes with belonging helps the teacher to better understand that he is on the right path." (T1)

"Appreciating and supporting the work done is a source of motivation for the teacher, getting positive results as a result of the work done makes the person feel important and unique." (T2)

Three of the teachers stated that feeling happy in the organization increased motivation. Some of their opinions are given below:

"Organizational culture existing in a school will undoubtedly increase the motivation of the teacher and the sense of belonging, which will affect the quality of the work done and the creation of a safer and happier working environment." (T5)

"In a happy and peaceful working area, the teacher aims to be effective for the student away from anxiety and turns into a learning teacher." (11)

Two of the teachers stated that materiality in the organization is important for teacher motivation, and one of their opinions is given below:

"Administrative management, content of the organization's expectations from the teacher, the salary paid to the teacher according to market prices, the delivery of personal rights to individuals, etc." (8)

Two of the teachers stated that being valued in the organization was important for teacher motivation, and one of their opinions is given below:

"Feeling that he is valued in the organization increases his motivation." (9)

Two of the teachers stated that acceptance in the organization is important for teacher motivation, and one of their opinions is given below:

"The teacher who adopts the organizational culture works efficiently in the organization. She feels safe. It becomes more productive." (3)

One of the teachers stated that student success in the organization was important in terms of teacher motivation, and the opinion on this is given below:

"He is also motivated by the success of his students. In addition to student success, teachers see their students' interest in the lesson as a motivating factor." (6)

4. To be done to improve the existing organizational culture

Participants' opinions on to be done to improve the existing organizational culture are shown as sub-themes in Table 4.

Tablo 5.

To be done to improve the existing organizational culture

Themes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	f
Right to speak		√	√	√		√	√	√			√	√	√	√	√	11
Communication	√			√					√	√						4
Activities									√					√		2
Materiality			√				√									2
Values					√											1
Positive Attitude		√														1
To appreciate	√															1

As seen in Table 5, eleven of the teachers stated that it was necessary and important to give importance to the ideas of teachers and to give more voice to the development of the organizational culture, and some of their opinions are given below:

"I think every teacher should have a say on this issue. The attitude of the organization towards the teachers is very important here, even the verbal mobbing of the teacher or the implication of dismissal causes the person not to express what he/she is uncomfortable with." (2)

"Teachers should be listened to, their ideas should be respected, and sexist approaches should be avoided. The teacher should be able to think about what I can produce rather than worrying about losing a job." (7)

"The ideas and discourses conveyed by the teachers in the organization in order to improve the current situation and bring solutions to the problems should be taken seriously by the administrative team." (8)

"In order to develop the existing organizational culture in private schools, it is necessary to plan for the future by analyzing the existing conditions and to listen to every idea." (12)

Four of the teachers stated that communication was necessary and important for the development of organizational culture, and some of their opinions are given below:

"There will certainly be mistakes, but style, communication will play an important role." (1)

"A respectable working environment, high communication activities, tendencies that will draw attention to the organizational culture should be done." (9)

Eleven of the teachers stated that it was necessary and important to give importance to the ideas of teachers and to give more voice to the development of the organizational culture, and some of their opinions are given below:

"I think every teacher should have a say on this issue. The attitude of the organization towards the teachers is very important here, even the verbal mobbing of the teacher or the implication of dismissal causes the person not to express what he/she is uncomfortable with." (2)

"Teachers should be listened to, their ideas should be respected, and sexist approaches should be avoided. The teacher should be able to think about what I can produce rather than worrying about losing a job." (7)

"The ideas and discourses conveyed by the teachers in the organization in order to improve the current situation and bring solutions to the problems should be seriously taken by the administrative team." (8)

"In order to develop the existing organizational culture in private schools, it is necessary to plan for the future by analyzing the existing conditions and to listen to every idea." (12)

Four of the teachers stated that communication was necessary and important for the development of organizational culture, and some of their opinions are given below:

"There will certainly be mistakes, but style, communication will play an important role." (one)

"A respectable working environment, high communication activities, tendencies that will draw attention to the organizational culture should be done." (9)

5. Metaphors on organizational culture

Participants' metaphors on organizational culture are shown as sub-themes in Table 4.

Table 6.

Metaphors on organizational culture

Themes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	f
Tree											√		√		√	3
Family					√	√						√				3
Sapling	√							√						√		3
Flower			√													1
Fire									√							1
Organism										√						1
Child							√									1
Jigsaw				√												1
Rule		√														1

As seen in Table 6, three of the teachers produced tree metaphor, and some of their opinions are given below:

"Organizational culture can be compared to a tree because if a tree clings to the soil with strong roots, it grows, develops and bears fruit. If the vision of the organizational culture is conveyed to the teacher clearly and correctly, the teacher grows, develops and bears fruit like a tree." (11)

"I liken the organization to a tree that grows when it is given the environment, care and water it needs. Because the tree is rooted and solid. It contributes to life with its shadow and fruits." (15)

Three of the teachers produced family metaphor, and some of their opinions are given below:

"The organization we exist in can be compared to our family. Just as the family is the most basic organization of the society and the most sincere feelings and atmosphere of trust are felt in our family, our organization where we spend most of our time should also have these characteristics. At its core, an environment of trust should be created, and happy individuals who can produce more in a constructive and supportive environment should be ensured." (5)

"Teachers in private schools may liken the organizational culture to a family culture. Teachers, who have great responsibility for the future, consider themselves the second parents of many children." (12)

Three of the teachers produced sapling metaphor, and the some of their opinions is given below:

"I can compare it to a sapling. Saplings grow and develop with a new system (Soil), love and discipline. Its roots grow stronger and continue to live. Organizations are like that. It develops with correct communication, vision and discipline, and lays its foundations firmly." (1)

One of the teachers produced flower metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“Organizational culture can be compared to a flower because if you provide the care it needs, it will grow, grow and become beautiful. For example, water should be given as much as it needs and the light it needs should be provided. If the organizational culture is transferred to the teacher as it should be, the teacher also develops and develops like a flower and can perform his profession in the most efficient way. This reflects positively on both the organization and the student.” (3)

One of the teachers produced fire metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“It can be compared to a fire around which people gather. And this fire rises with the ideas and belonging of everyone.” (9)

One of the teachers produced organism metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“Organizational culture in private schools can be compared to a living organism. While a well-founded organizational culture is a living organism that has evolved over millions of years, outside interventions against nature can be compared to unprincipled and daily policies. The fact that external interventions to the natural processes of living things and organisms should be done very carefully and after the experimental processes show that it is necessary to be very careful in order to create a settled culture in education and private school culture.” (10)

One of the teachers produced flower metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“Organizational culture can be compared to a flower because if you provide the care it needs, it will grow, grow and become beautiful. For example, water should be given as much as it needs and the light it needs should be provided. If the organizational culture is transferred to the teacher as it should be, the teacher also develops and develops like a flower and can perform his profession in the most efficient way. This reflects positively on both the organization and the student.” (3)

One of the teachers produced child metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“Corporate culture is like a child. Just as we can create a bond with our child by showing our love to our child, being there for him at every moment, giving him confidence, the corporate culture will create the same bond for the teacher.” (T7)

One of the teachers produced puzzle metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“All the activities done in the institution, the values, the vision of the institution are like pieces of a puzzle. The parts make up the whole. Every value that is made and established constitutes the whole.” (T4)

One of the teachers produced rule metaphor, and teacher's opinion is given below:

“We can liken corporate culture to the rules we have to comply with in all areas of life. Sometimes we have to comply even if it is not suitable for us.” (T2)

Discussion and conclusion

In this part of the study, the conclusions from the research findings are discussed. In this study, which was designed with a qualitative research model, the research results included only the opinions of the teachers who participated in the study and evaluated them in their own context. In the study, it was aimed to reveal the teachers' perspectives on the organizational culture, the connections between the

motivations of belonging and the organizational culture, the effects of the organizational culture on the motivation of the teachers, the effects and contributions of the teachers in the development of the organizational culture, and the teachers' views on what they compare the organizational culture to.

When the findings related to the first sub-problem of the research, the sub-problem of how teachers working in private schools define the concept of organizational culture, the concepts of values, vision, rules and principles, sense of belonging, communication between stakeholders, organizational mission, belief and organizational process were mentioned by teachers. The emergence, development and continuity of school culture and identity depended on the unity of stakeholders in organizations around common values and ensuring their continuity by internalizing the values. These findings were consistent with Richard (1999), who defined school culture as a whole consisting of in-school rules, beliefs and values that guided the behavior of administrators, teachers and students in a school, and with the views of Deal and Peterson (1999), who defined the school as an organization consisting of value judgments and belief patterns and traditions formed in the process since its establishment.

When the answers they gave to the problem of how do the teachers define their belonging to the institution, which is the second sub-problem of the research, were reviewed, they gave answers such as trust, materiality, spirituality, communication values, self-sacrifice, happiness, being appreciated.

Many answers were identified that kept the sense of belonging, which expressed the commitment of teachers to organizations, alive. It was found that the general nature of these responses was emotionally based. In this context, it could be said that, as in human relations, in unit-organization relations, people were more connected to the place where they felt safe and happy. This was only possible in organizations with a strong school culture. These findings were supported in by Genç's (1993) characteristics of schools with poor culture. Because in the study it was found that in schools with poor culture; the bonds between stakeholders (administrator, teacher, student and parent) weakened, trust towards each other decreased, dialogue weakened, motivation decreased, negative emotions and feelings of doubt became common, there were constant conflicts in the environment, communication and unity deteriorated and love-respect weakened. Accordingly, the issues that affected the teacher's belonging to the organization were also mentioned. Thus, while belonging weakened in organizations with poor culture, it increased in strong organizations.

In the third sub-problem of the research on the problem of opinions of the effects of organizational culture on teacher motivation, the teachers mentioned the factors such as trust, appreciation, happiness, material elements, feeling valuable, adopting and student success as concepts that affected both the organizational culture and the motivation of the teachers. Motivation is a very important feeling in professions and works done with emotion, conscience and effort. It is a concept that causes people to either cling to their work more tightly or give up. Therefore, in order to increase and protect the quality of service in the works done in the organizations, the motivation of the teachers should be kept at the forefront and various elements should be introduced in this way. As seen in the views by teachers to this sub-problem, mutual trust among school stakeholders was seen as the most important factor. Being appreciated and material values were also important elements in human motivation to feel valuable.

As for the fourth sub-problem of the research, what could be done to improve the existing organizational culture in private schools, views were giving the right to speak with active participation, communication, activities, materiality and making someone feel valuable, and positive attitude. Organizational culture in private schools generally came to the fore in terms of the quality and continuity of the service elements provided. This situation would be supported by the contribution of teachers who would keep the organizational culture alive and implement it. It came to the fore that teachers wanted to have a say as a participant in organizational events and sharing about their expectations so that they could contribute to the development of the organizational culture and had a say in order to be decisive and directing. People's efforts to improve something would only be easier when they became the determinant and internalization of that situation. These views emerged as a result of strong school culture, administrators and teachers

uniting around common values, norms and beliefs. It was also parallel with the views of Çelik (2000), that in schools where the cultural structure is strong, it is no longer necessary for people to supervise each other.

It was found that the participants produced metaphors such as tree, family, flower, fire, organism, child, jigsaw puzzle to the fifth sub-problem of the research, Participants likened the transformation from sapling to tree with the tree analogy, the organizational culture being firmly attached to its roots, and trees being tied to the soil with their roots. Organizational culture also symbolizes the commitment to the organization and its development. Organizational culture formation and development process can be compared to living organisms. As it is fed and its process is carried out, it will grow and develop and the dominance of the environment will increase. Those findings are consistent with Ceylan's (1998) views that just as the personalities of people differ, the cultures of institutions also differ. Because each institution's unique structure, employees and environment are also different.

Recommendations

Based on the data obtained as a result of study section, following suggestions were put forward:

The teachers of the organizations should take an active role, to organize activities in which there are rewards based on common values, meetings and determined criteria. This will both strengthen the bond and increase the quality of the work and service produced.

It is essential to plan activities such as various group activities, meetings, meals in order to create a bond of mutual trust, love and respect between the administration and teachers in the organizational structure. In addition, based on the fact that man is an emotional and social being, material and spiritual gestures that will make him feel good, peaceful and valuable can be offered as suggestions as they will strengthen his organizational identity and sense of belonging.

Human is both an emotional and social being, so people create a comfort zone for themselves, feel safe about themselves and their future, and are influenced by the stakeholders of the organization. It is important to feel accepted and valued. Such formations will prevent the weakening of the organizational culture and the harming of the ties between the stakeholders. It is recommended to provide these environments.

It is essential to give teachers a right to speak with active participation, as it is a quality-enhancing factor in terms of the quality and continuity of the service elements provided in the organizational culture.

Organizational managers should provide important developments in terms of the continuation and future of the organization by nurturing the culture and structure, creating environments that will provide clear participants and general happiness.

Organizations should create the organizational culture in line with a certain vision and mission and adopt an identity that is open to development regarding organizational culture and school culture.

Managers of the organizations that the stakeholders in the organization should always be active in the activities and value their opinions.

With the awareness of the importance of culture, it can be suggested that organizations should engage in activities and activities that will make them feel valuable to their employees, members and customers.

Founders and administrators of private schools that they make their teachers feel both happy and safe by promoting their teachers in the organizational structure, by offering them financial opportunities at the highest possible level. These opportunities will increase the quality of the service they will provide.

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Ethical Approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**Opinions of Teachers Working in Private Schools on Creating and Developing Organizational Culture**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data. “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Ethics Committee Approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 06 decision numbered 123 on March 25th, 2022.